

How much is \$1.43 worth?

Portal Admin

August 27, 2024

[WORLDVIEW]

The stated amount is apparently small when the actual purchasing power, in economic terms, is considered.

Nonetheless, when we talk about the amount of revenue from book sales, it can be significant. The reasons are going to be explained.

Title	Pages read
Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories	303
Pages read	
United States	207
Canada	90
India	6

Illustration. Amazon KENP for the title *Better Economics for the Earth* [1] as of Aug. 26, 2024.

Apart from book sales in terms of orders, with units being book copies sold, Amazon's sales closing system also helps authors sell book pages, if a book is enrolled in this sales mode under the Kindle Unlimited Program. Their sale unit is KENP (The Kindle Edition Normalized

Pages). Amazon “normalizes” a page read using its homegrown algorithm. Using a KENP converter, one can estimate the monetary value of 303 KENP in the figure to be equal to \$1.43.

That’s why it is not difficult to see the significance of this tiny amount of money.

To achieve this, valuable book reviews such as [2] are required. So how much time and effort can we expect from readers in order to have honest and quality reviews?

In addition, the figure also shows that readers who bought KENP came from different countries, at least the U.S., Canada, and India. (In fact, there may be more because Amazon lumps many markets into a single category of “the U.S.”.) For a 50-year-old author in Vietnam, the fact that an Indian or Canadian reader could read some pages of his book almost instantly was absolutely unthinkable just 20 years ago. This reality is a technological miracle, isn’t it?

So, for us, this little amount means a lot. The revenue, however small it is, is not bad at all.
Pas mal du tout!

References

[1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOD98L5K44>

[2] Napier NK. (2024). A power-packed treatise on economics and the environment. <https://philpapers.org/rec/NAPAPT>

